

Learning Technology Accelerator

LEA Web page

Deliverable D6.1

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ENTER.
European Network for Transfer and Exploitation of EU Project Results

D6.1 Lea Web page

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1. LEA WEB PAGE

A web page for the LEA project was developed at the beginning phase of the project in order to ensure LEA's public visibility right from the start and to kick-off T6.1. Communication with the LEARNTECH community. The website is conceived as a tool for dissemination, which will be used to inform the interested public, find and acquire LEA Followers, publish news and update anyone interested in the project. The website will also serve as a storage and documentation space for all project partners as well as evaluators of the EC. LEA-Network members will further on get access to LEA tools via this channel, so it additionally serves as a working space for the LEA-network.

LEA web page is a living document, which will be altered along the way as new developments in the project occur. This is vital, as it ensures an up-to-date website which will stay interesting to its visitors and which continuously displays the current state of the project.

The LEA project's Domain address:

<https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu>

The website is operated on a WordPress system and was designed and implemented by PM Datentechnik, an Austrian IT company. Alterations and changes to the website were done by P4 (ENTER) with consideration of the suggestions made by P1 (University of Jyväskylä) and P17 (EUPK) as well as the WP leaders group.

1.1 Start page

The start page includes several sections which all serve a specific purpose. They will be described individually, even though they are all part of the same page.

(i) Stakeholder description

The main four stakeholder groups in the LEA project are represented by individual icons (variations of the LEA logo) and each group is briefly described. The group icons can be clicked on and take the visitor to the respective stakeholder group's page. Additionally, a link to the IMAILE project's website is provided to connect LEA with IMAILE.

The screenshot shows the 'LEA STAKEHOLDERS' page. At the top left is the LEA logo and 'Learning Technology Accelerator'. At the top right are navigation links: 'News', 'Stakeholders', 'Follow LEA', and 'Partners' area'. The main content area is dark with the title 'LEA STAKEHOLDERS' in white. Below the title are four circular icons representing stakeholder groups: Procurers (pink squares), Suppliers (blue starburst), Learn Tech Experts (green square), and Schools (orange horizontal lines). Each icon has a corresponding title and a short description below it. At the bottom, it says 'BUILDING ON KNOWLEDGE FROM IMAILE' with the IMAILE logo.

(ii) LEA map

The LEA map illustrates the locations of organisations who are part of LEA's stakeholder network (partners + followers). Page visitors can click on the individual, highlighted countries on the map and will subsequently be taken to a map of the country they chose, showing all the organisations listed in that country.

(iii) Terminology

This section of the start page provides a terminology of some of the most important terms used in the LEA project. This is meant to be a helpful tool for website visitors who want to find out more about the project. Currently, the terms “PCP”, “PPI”, “PLE” and “LEA Followers” are listed and explained. This section is likely to grow over time, as more texts will be published on the website and thus more expressions requiring an explanation will occur. Additionally, this section includes a general explanation of the LEA project.

TERMINOLOGY

LEA Followers

LEA Followers consist of procurers, suppliers, learn tech experts and schools, who are all invited to join the project as observers, following the project activities and results, sharing their experiences and talking about lessons learned. Followers receive updates on the LEA project through newsletters and on the LEA website and they are welcome to participate in LEA capacity building seminars and other networking events.

PCP (PRE-COMMERCIAL PROCUREMENT)
PCP is a public procurement of research and development services. It is an important tool to stimulate innovation as it enables the public sector to steer the development of new solutions directly towards its needs.

PPI (PUBLIC PROCUREMENT OF INNOVATION)
PPI occurs when the public sector uses its purchasing power to act as an early adopter of innovative solutions which are not yet available on a large-scale commercial basis.

PLE (PERSONALISED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT)
PLEs are systems enabling students to control and define their own learning processes under the mentoring of a teacher. This includes adapted learning based on ability, skills, and goals. The PLE system allows connecting students, teachers, parents, and the wider community by means of open and commercial ICT solutions inside and outside the school facilities, supporting a lifelong learning process.

The LEA project's goal is to accelerate knowledge transfer, dialog and awareness raising of innovative procurement within the learning technology sector by creating a European wide learntech procurers' network. LEA is the first joint European PPI in the educational sector and wants to showcase the excellent opportunities for procurement of innovation within that sector. These innovative processes put users to the drivers' seat in technology development. The project brings competitive advantage to EU companies by raising their innovation to a market leader level. Solutions created through PPI can have valuable societal impact, e.g. early identification of school dropouts and exciting pupils for STEM careers. LEA will prepare a PPI call for tender continuing the challenges identified in the previous PCP "IMAILE" project as well as one extra PCP. The project started in March 2018 and will last for 2 years.

JOIN THE PROJECT

(iv) Project consortium

This start page section lists all partners in the project consortium including their name, logo, a brief partner description, and important contact details such as e-mail addresses, twitter handles, Facebook profiles and others.

PROJECT CONSORTIUM
 PROMOTERS AND EXPERT ORGANISATIONS FROM 9 EU MEMBER COUNTRIES

- UNIVERSITY OF JYVÄSKYLÄ
- INOVA+
- HALMSTAD KOMMUN
- ENTER
- UNIVERSITY OF OULU
- MUNICIPALITY OF RONNEBY
- SACHSEN-ANHALT
- OTTO-VON-GUERCKE-UNIVERSITÄT MAGDEBURG
- GÖTEBORGSREGIONEN
- ICLEI
- SARA BEDIH
- STARTUP EUROPE
- VILADEJANS
- COMUNE DI TORINO
- BRAGA
- INNOVA
- EURK - EU PROJEKTIONSGULT

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1.2 News

This section of the website features links to all available news items about the LEA project. This includes the news posted on the LEA web page itself as well as social media posts via an embedded social media stream. The news section is thus an ever-expanding collection news postings, which will grow over time. Featured social media posts include certain hash tagged keywords and other indicators connected to the LEA project.

The screenshot shows the LEA website's news section. At the top left is the LEA logo and navigation links: News, Stakeholders, Follow LEA, and Partners' area. Below the logo is a 'NEWS' heading and a search bar. A grid of news items is displayed, including:

- LEA AT EDTECH INDUSTRY MARKET EVENT**: LEA interacts at Swedish (Nordic) EDTECH industry market event.
- LEA - Learntech Accelerator**: updated their profile picture.
- RT @Kati_Clements**: What better way to motivate kids to STEM careers than self-made, mobile-controlled robots! @StimeyOn festival yesterday...
- RT @Educ_Technology**: Sam Blyth, director of #schools and further education at @CanvasLMS, says of #edtech: "The conversation needs to..."
- LEA AT ITK 2018**: The interactive technology in...
- Teachers unions**: in the coming years should play an increasingly vital role beyond the schoolyard, working with other community organizations to...
- Home - ITK 2018**
- RT @Kati_Clements**: What better way to motivate kids to STEM...

1.3 Stakeholders

The stakeholder section on the website is split up into four parts corresponding to the project's four stakeholder groups – procurers, suppliers, learn tech experts, and schools. This makes it possible to post targeted news individually for each of the groups. At the top of the page, a description of the respective stakeholder group is given including a list of benefits specifically for the that target group and a button inviting stakeholders to become Followers can be found directly underneath it – the button leads to the Followers' sign-up page. In addition to this, the posted news items will be listed chronologically and according to the group of interest. It is possible to “stick” one news item to the top of the page to display it on top at all times.

The screenshot shows the LEA website interface. At the top left is the LEA logo. In the top right corner, there are navigation links: 'News', 'Stakeholders', 'Follow LEA', and 'Partners' area'. The main content area features a green square icon with a white 'L' and the heading 'LEARNTECH EXPERTS'. Below this is a paragraph describing the role of learning technology experts. A sub-heading asks 'WHAT LEA CAN OFFER TO LEARNING TECHNOLOGY EXPERTS?' followed by a bulleted list of benefits. Below the list is a question 'DO YOU SPEAK BOTH TECHNOLOGY AND TEACHER/STUDENT LANGUAGE?' and contact information for Kati Clements. A blue button labeled 'Follow LEA here!' is positioned below the contact info. At the bottom of the screenshot, there is a section titled 'LEA AT EDTECH INDUSTRY MARKET EVENT' with logos for 'Swedish Edtech Industry' and 'edtech'.

1.4 Follow LEA

This page lists the benefits of being a Follower of the LEA project and provides the form necessary to become one. The organisations' details collected in this form are needed so that Followers can be provided with the mentioned benefits. Additionally, when someone signs up as a LEA Follower, they will also receive the LEA project's newsletter. For managing the newsletter mailings, *Newsletter 2 go* has been implemented. This system will be used to create templates, compose newsletters and send them to subscribers. Targeted newsletters for the individual stakeholder groups are possible.

[News](#)
[Stakeholders](#)
[Follow LEA](#)
[Partners' area](#)

BECOME A LEA FOLLOWER!

THESE ARE SOME OF YOUR BENEFITS:

- Learn about PCP, PPI, and Open Innovation in learning.
- Follow LEA results and lessons learned on a regular basis via newsletters, updates on the LEA project website and on social media.
- Influence and contribute to future European demand policies on innovative learning technology.
- Meet other stakeholders in the education sector, share your knowledge and learn from them.
- Attend capacity building seminars and network sessions organised by LEA free of charge.
- Public procurer organisations who are LEA Followers receive active support for their participation in LEA innovation procurement calls (LEA PPI / LEA PCP). This includes the development of legal tender documentation and guidance about funding opportunities of PPI/PCP on national/regional and EU levels for the public procurers' own organisations.

SIGN UP HERE TO BECOME A LEA FOLLOWER AND BE PART OF THE LEARNTECH ACCELERATOR COMMUNITY.

Organisation's name *

Organisation's website/URL *

Contact person (first name, last name) *

Contact e-mail *

Organisation's location (city) *

Organisation's postal code *

Organisation's country *

Please provide a short description of the organisation *

Types of organisation *

LearnTechExpert
 Procurer
 School
 Supplier

Logo upload

Keine Datei ausgewählt.

Please upload your logo here. Required specifications: square; max. 5 MB; *.jpg, *.gif, *.png

GDPR Agreement *

I consent to having this website store my submitted information so they can respond to my inquiry.

Check here to indicate that you have read and agree to the terms of our Data Use Policy, including our Cookie Use. *

Data protection policy - LEA (LearnTech accelerator)

This form enables you to join the LEA project as a Follower. It collects your name, the name of your organisation, your e-mail address, your residential country, a short description of your organisation, and you can upload your logo. By submitting this information and checking the box above, you agree that your organisation and the mentioned data will be shown in the LEA-Network map, which is publicly accessible. Additionally, you will automatically receive the LEA newsletter via email.

Your data will be stored at a local server and used in the course of the LEA project exclusively; At all times, you have the right to demand information about your data and you

1.5 LEA Consortium Partners' area

The partners' area on the website functions as an internal web space, and will be accessible to the partners and the Commission only. Partners can use this area as a space for storage and documentation of project results, entering it by logging in with their unique user name and password. As of now, this internal space is not yet filled, as the documents are only being created at this point. Examples of the files that will be stored and shared in the partners' area are the project Deliverables, which will be uploaded to this area once they have been submitted; over time, the partners' area will thus become more comprehensive as new items are added continuously.

1.6 Header and footer

The website is completed by a header (with the project logo and a navigation menu) and a footer (including the EU disclaimer & statement and contact information for the LEA project).

Header

Footer

2. MOBILE VERSION

The LEA website was built in a responsive design in order to be also easily available for smartphones and tablets. On the mobile version, the LEA page can be navigated with the help of a burger menu at the top left corner of the page.

Screenshots of the LEA web page mobile version; start page

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Mobile news section

Example of the mobile stakeholder section

Mobile Follower sign-up form

Mobile partners' area

Mobile navigation – burger menu

3. THE LEA LOGO

The logo for the LEA project was developed and designed by P13 (Viladecans). The logo and the matching corporate identity form the basis for the website's design, which is why some more details will be given about the logo and its variations.

The following key concepts and ideas were integrated into the logo: acceleration, dialogue, change/innovation/modernisation, networking, learning technologies, and education. The logo's typography was kept modern, simple, and round and as colours, a neutral grey tone and two shades of yellow were chosen.

3.1 Logo variations

Four different variations for the logo were developed – one for each stakeholder group. These variations all stay within the general design style and feature individual details representing the specific aspects of the respective groups.

4. CONCLUSION

The LEA web page is a living document that will be maintained and updated throughout the entire LEA project period. Over time, there will be more information and more input gathered, which will result in more web content. As project events take place and as LEA participates in other events such as exhibitions, conferences, and presentations, there will be new content generated and updates to the LEA web page will be made. As of now, the web page is ready to operate, in coherence with the LEA brand identity. LEA web page will function as a hub for LEA network members to get access to new information: Capacity building seminars, trainings, Open Market Consultation coming up etc.

